

Terrorism versus Transnational Organized Crime as threats to nations and societies.

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Summary: *This paper looks at the perceived and real threats to nations and societies by terrorism and by transnational organized crime, and then at the international response to these issues by nations and the international community to help inform the discussion about which represents the greatest threat, and what we are doing about it.*

In 2009 an Australian criminology academic said that “Terrorism is a violent - and irritating - distraction from the overall ongoing struggle against organised crime, which constitutes a far greater, long term and permanent threat to nations and societies”. This quote is something of a “wake-up call” for legislators, leaders in the law enforcement, security and intelligence fields.

While global attention has been focused on the “War on terror” since the al-Qaeda sponsored attacks on the World Trade Centre towers in New York on September 2001, massive amounts of fiscal, technical and human resources have been focused on this issue.

However, this quote begs the question: Have we “taken our eye off the ball”, and consequently lost sight of the larger threat that is transnational organized crime (TOC), or is terrorism an extension or expansion of organized crime, to which we need to assign additional resources.

However, if we have been “distracted”, what has been the cause, and can we undertake a “course correction”, and should we.

Why did we get “distracted” - Methods versus motives?

While we see many discussions emerging today which speak to terrorism being an extension of TOC, they tend to focus on the methods of operations, and the consequential impact on communities.

International terrorist operations require monetary resources to undertake, and those expenses range from technical support, to travel to equipment. Therefore we should not be surprised to see international terrorist organizations using criminal activities to fund such operations, with criminal activities ranging from fraud, and kidnapping, through to trafficking in drugs, guns, people and even human organs.

Conversely, we have seen TOC groups using terrorist's tactics to achieve their goals by terrorizing communities into compliance or terrorizing law enforcement and prosecutors into ignoring their activities. As an example, the drug cartels in Colombia have used IED, mortars, grenades and improvised rockets (Gallego 2009) against the military and government counter-narcotic operations, at a level that was only outpaced by Islamic terrorist groups in Iraq and Afghanistan at the height of those conflicts (U.S. Department of Defense 2014).

However, while we see a cross-over in methods and activities between TOC and international Terrorist groups, there are two fundamental issues that both distinguish their activities and their goals.

TOC activities around the globe are generally covert, participants in these activities try to remain in the shadows of society, and do not attempt to draw public attention to themselves, and certainly do not want mass media attention, which it turn draws government and law enforcement resources and activities.

International terrorist groups operate overtly, seeking public and mass media attention, which they utilize as a force multiplier, to create broader public fear, and increase the perception of their power and reach.

Further, while we should not be surprised to see a cross over in activities between groups in these two spheres, we need to be cognizant that the motivation of these two spheres is quite distinct.

In the case of international terrorist groups, money is used as an enabler, providing resources for activities that will extend their influence, control or power. While the accumulation of wealth and its materialistic trappings consistently appears to be the motivation of organized crime. This was underscored during the 2007 raid on the Mexico City residence of one of the largest drug producers which netted 4,500 lbs of U.S. currency, totalling about \$205.6 million US dollars (Tobar & Martinez 2007). The money had not been invested or utilized, but rather was simply hoarded and stored on site suggesting that simply amassing wealth was the ultimate goal.

International terrorism continues to be focused on political or philosophical outcomes, while TOC continues to be focused on the accumulation of wealth.

How did we get “distracted”? – The mass media and public opinion.

Within communities across North America and Europe, public opinion seems clearly focused on terrorism as the predominant threat to national security and personal safety. This public opinion impacts lawmakers and politicians that are attempting to respond to the concerns of their constituents, as well as government agencies that are in turn attempting to respond to the requests or directions of their political masters.

In a 2013 presentation at the Brookings institute, former CIA Counterterrorism Analysis Center Deputy Director Philip Mudd said “the American people don’t have an appetite for death as a result of terrorism” ...”we (the American people) don’t have the resilience to handle a kid with an AK47 in a mall” ...”people in this country will accept violent crime at an incredible rate, they won’t accept terrorism” (Mudd 2013).

Terrorism and mass media in the west are intrinsically linked and have a symbiotic relationship. Major media outlets become the voice of terrorist organizations and terrorism in general. Breaking news reports and up-to-the-minute news updates generate a sense of “need to know” amongst the news consumers, and that is feed by sensational events that are repeated and re-spun through the news cycle.

A study conducted through the University of California, concluded that “...vivid traumatic images from the media could lead to long-lasting negative consequences” and that the studies “...findings provide persuasive evidence that widespread media coverage of terrorism and war may have harmful effects on mental and physical health over time” (Anon n.d.)

As a result, isolated events of terror take on disproportionate perception in the minds of the news consumers, who see the same event, through multiple lenses, resulting in a disproportionate sense of fear and threat, which is consistent with the goal of terrorism.

Terrorism is not just a social, political and national distraction, it is also major revenue generator for the news and entertainment industry.

However, when we look at virtually every other indicator of threats to our economies and the safety of our communities, be it economic impact, locations impacted, number of people impacted, all the way through to number of deaths resulting from their activities, the threat and

impact pendulum would swing dramatically away from international terrorism and towards Transnational Organized Crime.

This distraction, away from TOC, is also being fueled by the linkages that are evolving between TOC and International Terrorism, where we see international terrorist groups securing funds through drug trafficking, human trafficking, and extortion along with many other activities that have historically been the domain of organized crime. As a result, we are seeing many more discussions emerging about the connection between TOC and international terrorism, this in turn has allowed government agencies to reallocate resources normally assigned to TOC investigations to be assigned to international terrorism investigations, especially in the area of financial system integrity, including money laundering.

The consequences of distraction – “Where did all the policemen go?”

However, the practical impact of this distraction has resulted in the reallocation of fiscal resources from many countries from international law enforcement efforts to the much more expensive military operations allocated to counter international terrorism.

While this was likely most pronounced in the United State, there appears to be little discussions of the reallocation of resources during the Presidency of George W. Bush. However, the issue started to gain public profile when then president-elect Barak Obama was preparing to take on the Presidency of the United States. A Washington Post article highlighted the significance of the shift of resources, stating that “Since the Sept. 11, 2001, attacks, more than 7 percent of the (Federal Justice) department's budget shifted to terrorism, away from drug trafficking, organized crime and white-collar misdeeds” (Johnson 2008).

Over time, this issue migrated to one of national concern for the countries legislators, as the U.S. Congressional Research Service 2010 report identified that “According to the Department of Justice and the FBI, the threats posed by organized crime have become more broad and complex than ever before. Federal resources dedicated to organized crime matters, however, do not appear to have expanded along with the threats, and have actually decreased since 2001. After the September 11, 2001, terrorist attacks, national priorities, including those of federal law enforcement, shifted further toward counterterrorism-related activities and further away from traditional crime fighting activities” (Finklea 2009, p.11)

Even the internal audits of the U.S Federal Bureau of Investigation identified this as an unexpected trend, when in the Office of the Inspector General’s 2010 report, he said “However the FBI used significantly fewer field agents than allocated on national priorities six through eight – criminal enterprises, white collar crime and violent crime...we also found that the FBI reduced the number of active cases between FYs 2005 and 2009 related to ...white collar crime, and violent crime” (Department of Justice - Office of the Inspector General 2010, p.8).

In 2012, the report from the U.S. Congressional Research Service again emphasized the impact of the distraction that international terrorism had on the allocation of law enforcement resources, stating that “Since the terrorist attacks of September 11, 2001, there has been a shift in law enforcement attention and resources toward counterterrorism-related activities and away from traditional crime fighting activities including the investigation of organized crime” (Bjelopera, J. 2012.)

TOC as a threat.

If both the UK and US governments see transnational organized crime as a national security threat, how large is the threat and does it pose a “long term and permanent threat to nations and societies”.

In the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime’s (UNODC) 2009 research report *Estimating illicit financial flows resulting from drug trafficking and other transnational organized crimes*, following their detailed analysis, “suggests that all criminal proceeds are likely to have amounted to some 3.6 per cent of GDP (2.3 - 5.5 per cent) or around US\$2.1 trillion in 2009” (United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime 2011, p.9).

While that is a significant figure (based on the International Monetary Funds, World Economic outlook Database, this equates roughly to the combined GDP of the worlds’ 96 poorest countries) it perhaps pales when we examine the UNODC reports numbers on people engaged or impacted by TOC activities. In just the area of cocaine, the report estimates that there are just over 2.6 million people involved in the trafficking of cocaine, to support a global user group of about 15.7 million.

Conversely, the U.S. State department lists 59 international terrorist groups that have been identified by the U.S. government. In the opening of the National Counterterrorism Center 2011 Report on Terrorism, the global impact of terrorist activities is quantified at “over 10,000 terrorist attacks occurred in 2011, affecting nearly 45,000 victims in 70 countries and resulting in over 12,500 deaths.”(Office of the Director of National Intelligence - NCTC 2011, p.9) The report goes on to provide nationalities of victims, identifying 17 U.S. private citizens died as a result of terrorist attacks in 2011.

During the same period however, in just the United States, the FBI estimate that “there are approximately 1.4 million active street, prison, and OMG gang members comprising more than Terrorism versus Transnational Organized Crime as threats to nations and societies.

33,000 gangs in the United States.” (Federal Bureau of Investigation 2011) According to the FBI Uniform Crime Reports for 2011, 12,664 murders occurred in the United States (Federal Bureau of Investigation 2011), more than the global loss of life through terrorist events, and of these 1,824 are gang-related homicides (National Gang Center 2012), merely one element of organized crime in the United States.

If we look at the impact of terrorism, in terms of violent deaths, versus regions that are racked with organized crime related corruption and violence, a recent Foreign Policy article articulated the chasm that exists between these two branches of violence, “in ... Afghanistan, in the midst of a violent insurgency in the south and east of the country, has a higher rate of violence still — nearly 10 violent deaths per 100,000 population. Yet for truly striking levels of violence, look at Central America — around 40 violent deaths per year for every 100,000 in the population across the region. Honduras was 90 annual deaths per 100,000” (Stavridis 2015).

Can we refocus on TOC.

The threat from TOC is therefore significant to nations and societies. However, do we as a society see that? Do our governments, our leaders and our institutions see that?

In the United Kingdom, where the counter terrorism and organized crime investigations mandates tend to fall to different agencies, the government felt that organized crime investigations were too disjointed, even with the existence of the UK’s Serious Organized Crime Agency (SOCA). When the UK government introduced legislation to create the current National Crime Agency (NCA), then Home Secretary Theresa May wrote in her opening of the report to Parliament, that “Last year’s National Security Strategy recognised that organised crime is one of the greatest threats to our national security... but the current response is patchy and fragmented” (Secretary of State for the Home Department 2011, p.4).

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With that, the government introduced one of the most profound changes to policing in the U.K. since the inception of the modern police force, by assigning authority to direct police operations and the assignment of police resources to the new head of the NCA.

U.S President Barack Obama has also gone on to commission a national strategy to combat transnational organized crime, and as a result, the U.S. National Security Council has stated that “Transnational organized crime (TOC) poses a significant and growing threat to national and international security, with dire implications for public safety, public health, democratic institutions, and economic stability across the globe”

Former U.S. Attorney General Michael Mukasey, reconvened the Organized Crime Council (AGOCC) in 2008, for the first time in 15 years, to address the national security threat posed by TOC. The AGOCC is chaired by the Deputy Attorney General and consists of the Assistant Attorney General for the Criminal Division, the chair of the Attorney General’s Advisory Committee and the leaders of nine participating federal law enforcement agencies, which include: the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), Immigration and Customs Enforcement (ICE), the Drug Enforcement Administration (DEA); the Internal Revenue Service (IRS), the Bureau of Alcohol Tobacco and Firearms (ATF), the U.S. Secret Service, the United States Postal Inspection Service (USPIS); U.S. Department of State, Bureau of Diplomatic Security; and U.S. Department of Labor, Office of the Inspector General.

The AGOCC went on to recommend the creation of a new International Organized Crime Intelligence and Operations Center (IOC-2), aimed at coordinating the TOC efforts of the U.S. federal law enforcement community.

These are significant efforts by major elements of the international law enforcement community to refocus their efforts on the growing threat posed by TOC, which they have stated, constitutes the most significant threat to national security and community safety.

Conclusions

In 2009, when the Australian criminology academic wrote that “Terrorism is a violent - and irritating - distraction from the overall ongoing struggle against organised crime, which constitutes a far greater, long term and permanent threat to nations and societies”, governments were starting to become aware of their need to turn their attention and resources back to the work of combatting transnational organized crime.

Today, there is an even greater awareness and appreciation of the impact that globalization has had on the TOC world, especially in the areas of money laundering, fraud, unreported income and counterfeit products, all of which have a major impact upon national economies.

So, while the global response to counter terrorism continues to improve, we now see more resources being refocused on the longer term and more impactful problem that is organized crime.

However, following the impact of the global financial crisis of 2008, which has left many of the world’s economies in a fragile state, coupled with the frailty of Central American democracies, and the continued staggering loss of life in Mexico, we are reminded that we overlook or ignore TOC activities at our peril. Organized crime activities will continue to undermine nations, societies and communities around the globe, and political and law enforcement leaders around the globe must always be mindful of the balance of resources that are required to keep both TOC and international terrorist in check. Our Australian criminology academic was quite write

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when he wrote that “organised crime...constitutes a far greater, long term and permanent threat to nations and societies” in 2009.

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